

Functioning Retroperitoneal Paraganglioma, Paracaval in Location: Complete Resection Without Vascular Graft Interposition. Case Report.

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ABSTRACT

Retroperitoneal paragangliomas are rare neuroendocrine tumors derived from neural crest cells. When functional, they secrete catecholamines that cause severe hypertensive crises. Their location near the inferior vena cava increases the complexity of surgical treatment.

We present the clinical case of a 60-year-old female patient with a history of partial nephrectomy for renal carcinoma and chronic diseases, such as diabetes and hypertension. She presented with recurrent episodes of palpitations, sustained tachycardia, diaphoresis, and anxiety. Imaging revealed a solid-cystic paracaval mass, in addition to the presence of plasma metanephrines, confirming its functionality. Complete resection was performed prior to pharmacological treatment with alpha- and beta-adrenergic blockers. Timely diagnosis, multidisciplinary evaluation, and adequate preoperative preparation allow for safe surgical resection without major complications.

KEYWORDS: Paraganglioma, functional tumor, catecholamines, retroperitoneum, hypertensive crisis, oncologic surgery.

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INTRODUCTION

Paragangliomas are rare neuroendocrine tumors derived from neural crest cells, also known as extraadrenal pheochromocytomas. They arise from paraganglia in various anatomical sites, including the head, neck, thorax, and abdomen. Retroperitoneal paragangliomas represent less than 0.1% of all neoplasms and between 21.5 and 87% of all paragangliomas (1, 2, 3).

Paragangliomas are characterized by excessive secretion of catecholamines, such as epinephrine, norepinephrine, and dopamine, which can cause clinical symptoms such as episodic hypertension, tachycardia, and diaphoresis (4, 5).

Functional retroperitoneal paraganglioma, especially those located in the paracaval region, is a challenge due to its clinical behavior and preoperative misdiagnosis. Its surgical technique is difficult given its proximity to large vessels, as intraoperative manipulation can cause a sudden release of

catecholamines, generating severe hemodynamic compromise with disastrous consequences (2, 6).

Diagnosis should include a biochemical evaluation, requesting plasma and urinary metanephrine levels, and imaging studies (CT and/or MRI) (7, 8).

Surgical treatment consists of radical resection, and in cases of severe adherence to the inferior vena cava, reconstruction with a prosthetic vascular graft will be considered, especially in experienced centers. Some authors recommend performing preoperative embolization before complete tumor excision (9, 10, 11, 12).

Definitive treatment is surgical, but requires careful medical preparation to avoid hypertensive crises or severe intraoperative and postoperative hypotension (13, 14, 15).

In the present study, a complete resection of a hyperfunctioning paracaval paraganglioma was performed, which had severe intraoperative hemodynamic repercussions,

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which were controlled with medical management, with a second attempt at reintervention, thus achieving surgical management.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 60-year-old female patient with no history of smoking or alcohol use was diagnosed with low-grade clear cell carcinoma of the left kidney treated with partial nephrectomy. She had a history of diabetes and systemic arterial hypertension and was treated with insulin, telmisartan, and atenolol.

She came to the clinic for sudden episodes of prolonged palpitations lasting more than 12 hours, associated with dizziness, nausea, sweating, tremors, and anxiety. Physical examination revealed persistent tachycardia of up to 150 bpm and sustained hypotension of 80/40 mmHg.

Additional studies were ordered, including an electrocardiogram with Holter monitoring, which showed sinus tachycardia and no major arrhythmias.

A contrast-enhanced CT scan revealed a heterogeneous solid lesion with arterial enhancement, measuring 3.9 x 5.6 cm, located in the paracaval region. An MRI was ordered to assess extension, reporting a heterogeneous oval image with solid-cystic behavior and heterogeneous post-contrast enhancement, measuring 42 x 44 x 38 mm, adjacent to the IVC, with no evidence of invasion into vascular structures (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. Contrast-enhanced MRI of the upper abdomen. In the retroperitoneum, dependent on the inferior vena cava (blue arrow), located superior to the entrance of the renal veins, an oval image is seen, with defined margins, heterogeneous with cystic-solid behavior, heterogeneous enhancement after application of the contrast medium, measuring 42 x 44 x 38 mm (yellow arrow).

Routine laboratory results showed normal results, but suspecting a functioning lesion, plasma metanephrine was ordered, reporting values of 238 pg/ml.

Initial management included medical preparation with amiodarone, bisoprolol, and prazosin. However, during the

first surgical attempt, she experienced an intraoperative hypertensive crisis of 280/120 mmHg upon manipulation of the tumor, necessitating the cancellation of the procedure.

It was decided to restart strict adrenergic blockade. During the second procedure, anesthesia was inducted with fentanyl, propofol, and vecuronium, and intubation was successful. During tumor manipulation, a new hypertensive crisis of 240/110 mmHg occurred, managed with nitroglycerin and esmolol infusion, achieving regular blood pressure levels, with complete tumor resection (Figures 2 and 3).

FIGURE 2. Intraoperative image: Retroperitoneal paracaval region, solid and cystic tumor measuring 4 x 3 x 4 cm. Adjacent to the inferior vena cava.

FIGURE 3. Surgical specimen. Completely resected paracaval tumor. The tumor measures 4.5 cm along its longest axis and 3 cm wide, with a lobulated contour and a smooth external surface, reddish-brown-purple in color, and firm to the touch.

Following complete resection, she developed severe hypotension managed with norepinephrine and adrenaline boluses. She was transferred to the ICU in stable condition, without major complications. During her stay in the ICU, she remained stable on low-dose norepinephrine for 24 hours.

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She was subsequently referred to the General Surgery Department with good postoperative progress. Discharge was decided due to good progress.

After a one-month follow-up visit, the patient was admitted with no catecholaminergic symptoms and an uncomplicated wound, with histopathological results consistent with paraganglioma (Figures 4 and 5).

FIGURE 4. Macroscopic image. The section reveals a mostly homogeneous solid surface with focal areas of hemorrhage and necrosis. Tumor parenchyma is grayish-brown in appearance, firm in consistency, and has few areas of fibrosis, suggesting a paraganglioma.

FIGURE 5. Microscopic images consistent with paraganglioma: vascularized solid nodules with a Zellballen-like pattern, chromaffin cells with extensive granular cytoplasm and vesicular nuclei, surrounded by sustentacular cells. Positive for chromogranin A, synaptophysin, and S-100 protein staining of sustentacular cells, consistent with a benign paraganglioma. No signs of malignant atypia, necrosis, or elevated Ki-67 expression were evident.

DISCUSSION

Retroperitoneal paragangliomas represent a rare clinical entity, most of the published cases correspond to case reports or case series in specialized centers, whose deep location and

endocrinologically active behavior sometimes make diagnosis and surgical management difficult. Although most are located in the paraaortic region or adjacent to the adrenal glands, cases with a paracaval location, such as the one presented here, are even rarer and pose significant technical challenges due to their proximity to major vascular structures, such as the inferior vena cava (1, 2).

Our case corresponds to a functional paraganglioma, diagnosed in a patient with no family history or known hereditary syndromes, which is consistent with previous reports indicating that more than 50% of paragangliomas appear sporadically (3, 4, 5).

Unlike extensive series where left-sided lesions predominate (possibly due to the anatomical orientation of the aorta), in this case the tumor was closely related to the inferior vena cava, posteriorly positioned, displacing vascular structures without invading them, allowing for complete resection without requiring a vascular graft (7, 10).

Clinically, the patient presented with symptoms characteristic of catecholaminergic secretion (headache, sweating, and paroxysmal tachycardia), which facilitated diagnostic suspicion and allowed for adequate preoperative preparation with adrenergic blockade, essential for preventing intraoperative hypertensive crises. This precaution has been widely documented as a key step in the management of functional paragangliomas (6, 8, 11, 14).

In previous studies, surgical resection has been established as the only curative treatment with a positive impact on survival, even in the presence of metastases. In our case, resection was performed without major vascular complications, despite the complex anatomical location, which was achieved through adequate surgical planning and preoperative imaging evaluation. This aspect reinforces the importance of the combined use of contrast-enhanced tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, and functional studies, such as catecholamine determination, to achieve an accurate diagnosis (11, 12, 13, 14, 15).

Surgical treatment of functioning tumors requires intensive pharmacological preparation. Prior alpha-adrenergic blockade, followed by beta-blockade if tachycardia is present, is essential to prevent intraoperative seizures. In cases of incomplete resection or malignant tumors, treatment with radionuclides or tyrosine kinase inhibitors may be considered (7, 8, 9).

Histopathologically, the tumor was positive for neuroendocrine markers consistent with a benign paraganglioma. No signs of malignant atypia, necrosis, or elevated Ki-67 expression were evident, indicators frequently associated with aggressive behavior. However, due to the known biological unpredictability of these tumors, prolonged follow-up, ideally lifelong, with periodic clinical, biochemical, and imaging studies is recommended (1, 4, 5).

In this case, the outcome was favorable thanks to adequate multidisciplinary preparation. Complete resection and the

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disappearance of subsequent catecholaminergic symptoms support curative control of the disease.

This case highlights that, although rare, paracaval paragangliomas should be considered in the differential diagnosis of functional retroperitoneal masses (1, 2). Adequate preoperative evaluation and a careful surgical strategy can allow complete resection without the need for vascular reconstruction, even in anatomically challenging regions.

CONCLUSION

Functional paracaval paraganglioma is a rare entity with the potential for severe hypertensive crises. Early recognition, a thorough evaluation, and a planned surgical strategy are key to avoiding complications and achieving favorable outcomes. This case exemplifies the importance of multidisciplinary work in the management of functional retroperitoneal tumors.

ABBREVIATIONS: Computed tomography (CT), Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), millimeter of mercury (mmHg), beats per minute (bpm), millimeters (mm), picograms (pg), intensive care unit (ICU), inferior vena cava (IVC).

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